

MOBILE MULTIMEDIA DEVICES AT A FOREIGN LANGUAGE LESSON AT A TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY

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Abstract

The use of multimedia technologies in the classroom has attracted scholars for at least the past two decades. Most of the research focuses on Internet resources, Internet multimedia or CDs. The article discusses some features of the use of mobile multimedia devices in a foreign language lesson at a technical university.

Keywords

mobile devices, benefit, communicate, digital age, effective assistants, learning process.

Introduction:

The discussions that are taking place regarding the appropriateness of using multimedia mobile devices in the classroom are mainly focused on whether students should be able to use their smartphones and tablets in the classroom and whether teachers should use their smartphones in the classroom for educational purposes. There are the pros and cons of using mobile multimedia devices:

- mobile multimedia devices distract from the lesson; - encourage cheating;
- teachers lose time trying to keep track of students;
- students can post photos and videos taken in class on the Internet;
- students already spend too much time on them. With all of the above in mind, we still cannot ignore the fact that our students carry a powerful computing device in their pocket. Not many educational institutions can keep up with technological progress and ensure the availability of state-of-the-art computers in the classroom; those that are available are quickly becoming obsolete. At the same time, most students have the latest smartphones with Internet access.

Main part:

The results of studies conducted among technical university students show that a significant part of the time that students spend on the Internet, they spend on

reading and writing. This is exactly what teachers are trying to achieve from them, therefore, there is an opportunity to extract some benefit from this. Teachers can take advantage of the fact that students already have multimedia skills and help them use these skills in learning a foreign language. The use of multimedia mobile devices in general allows enriching the experience of students in using them as effective assistants in the learning process. Let's take a look at how advanced different age groups are in terms of mobile media usage. The most advanced are teenagers and young adults 18-2. Due to the fact that they grew up in the "digital age", they have developed fundamentally different communication and multimedia skills compared to older people [10,405]. Knowing these statistics, many teachers believe that their students are much more advanced in this regard than they are, so they are reluctant to use multimedia mobile devices in the classroom. Is this statement true? Studies have shown that the majority of teenagers use multimedia mobile devices for entertainment purposes, many of them are not even familiar with Web 2.0, designed for creating information and information exchange.

Why do they use multimedia technologies?

Phone calls 3%;

Communication in social networks or messaging (Telegram, Instagram, etc.) more than 90%; Email writing 2%; Exchange of photos and video messages, commenting on photos 10% . Teachers, on the contrary, use them to solve current educational problems, increase the productivity of the educational process, and also as a teaching tool, respectively, they are more oriented in the educational capabilities of multimedia devices [9, 1790].

It's a good idea to develop a so-called "classroom mode" - classroom mode (similar to "flight mode"-flight mode). Using a smartphone in the classroom (limited) mode implies blocking access to social networks, generally allowing the device to be used only to solve the tasks set by the teacher. Why can a teacher use multimedia mobile devices in the classroom? Much depends on what kind of tasks the teacher sets for students, to encourage them to use multimedia in order to solve educational problems, as well as on the way multimedia technologies are introduced into the learning process. In the vast majority of cases, these tasks come down to finding information, teachers rarely give students tasks that stimulate creativity [39,218]. The main types of work with multimedia (BYOD - "bringyourowndeviceactivities") include: taking notes, audio or video recording of lesson fragments, searching for information on the Internet (Wikipedia, Wikihow, Googlesearch), using various educational applications, world time, world weather,

ABBYlingo, MerriamWebsteronline dictionaries, McMillandictionaryonline, YouTube resource with various educational purposes: access to video lessons and videos on various topics, songs in a foreign language, etc., access to British council educational resources - any kind of interactive tasks, games, podcasts with transcripts and tasks for them, saving and exchanging information using Dropbox servers, participating in a video conference with another educational institution, virtual walks in world museums, Googleearth services, etc. [24]. There are multimedia created specifically for classroom use.

Most modern textbooks contain tools and resources for educators, such as integrated videos. The purpose of their use is to try to ensure that the thematic video fit harmoniously into the lesson, and not be a separate element of it, in addition, students have the opportunity to see how people communicate in different situations, facial expressions, facial expressions, gestures, which together allows create a stable model of speech behavior [33,205].

Modern study guides also contain other types of integrated interactive content, allowing students to complete exercises and tests together and instantly see the result of their work. The use of an instant check system is important for students due to the fact that each of them has the opportunity to see the result of a personalized check and get a grade immediately after completing the exercises, without having to wait for the next lesson. The use of such a system in the classroom also significantly saves the teacher's time [26, 1985]. Teachers can download additional grammar and vocabulary exercises, presentation sets available on the publishers' websites. Websites that specialize in a range of resources for educators provide the ability to download video and audio stories and transcripts, projects, test generators, and more. (www.onestopenglish.com, www.britishcouncil.ru) Using the content offered on the websites of publishers, the teacher gets the opportunity to see the process of students completing assignments, which exercises they have completed, in which cases additional work on the material is needed, etc. Doing projects is also a good way to integrate media into the classroom. Examples of projects that naturally integrate multimedia in the classroom are the following projects: creating a photo story, dubbing a movie, recording audio in accordance with the topic of the lesson (in a company, in a car service, etc., in a store, at an exhibition) [27,288].

Conclusion:

All this can inspire teachers and their students to use more multimedia in the classroom. The use of mobile multimedia devices for classroom teaching of a foreign language is just one of the methods that stimulate the motivation of

students in developing foreign language skills, the integration of multimedia in the teaching and learning process, the use of technology improves the overall quality of teaching and learning foreign languages.

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